

POST-COVID-19 MICROBIOTA ALTERATIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON HOST IMMUNITY

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Abstract. Beyond the respiratory system, COVID-19 infection has systemic consequences that affect the gut microbiota and gastrointestinal tract. In this study, alterations in gut bacteria composition and function were investigated following SARS-CoV-2 infection. Apart from that, it was observed that short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) had been faced with dramatic decrease while antimicrobial-resistant bacteria, particularly *Klebsiella* species, had grown. These changes are believed to be intimately related to neurological, respiratory, immunological, and gastrointestinal problems.

Key words: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, microbiota, gut-brain, lung-brain, post-COVID complications, gastrointestinal (GI) tract

Annotatsiya. Nafas olish tizimidan tashqari, COVID-19 infeksiyasi ichak mikrobiotasi va ovqat hazm qilish traktiga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan tizimli oqibatlariga ega. Ushbu tadqiqotda SARS-CoV-2 infeksiyasidan so'ng ichak bakteriyalari tarkibi va funksiyasidagi o'zgarishlar o'rganildi. Bundan tashqari, qisqa zanjirli yog' kislotalari (SCFA) keskin kamaygani, antimikrobiyal qarshilikka ega bakteriyalar, xususan *Klebsiella* turlari esa ko'paygani kuzatildi. Ushbu o'zgarishlar asab tizimi, nafas olish, immun va ovqat hazm qilish tizimlari bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin deb hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, mikrobiota, ichak-miya, o'pka-miya, post-COVID asoratlari, ovqat hazm qilish (GI) trakti

Аннотация. Помимо дыхательной системы, инфекция COVID-19 имеет системные последствия, затрагивающие кишечную микробиоту и желудочно-кишечный тракт. В данном исследовании были изучены изменения в составе и функции кишечных бактерий после заражения SARS-CoV-2. Кроме того, было выявлено значительное снижение уровня короткоцепочечных жирных кислот (SCFA), тогда как количество антимикробно-резистентных бактерий, в частности представителей рода *Klebsiella*, увеличилось. Считается, что эти изменения тесно связаны с неврологическими, дыхательными, иммунологическими и желудочно-кишечными нарушениями.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, микробиота, ось кишечник-мозг, ось лёгкие-мозг, постковидные осложнения, желудочно-кишечный тракт (ЖКТ)

Introduction. The severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is the distinct beta-coronavirus responsible for coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), a worldwide outbreak that affected over five million people until November 2021 [1]. The respiratory system exhibits the greatest number of COVID-19 symptoms, with extrapulmonary manifestations such as cardiac dysfunction, thrombotic issues, and gastrointestinal (GI) symptoms becoming common [2]. SARS-CoV-2 needs ACE2 to identify and access cells, and it may have an impact on immune and metabolic activity. Intestinal cells, an important location for virus entrance into the intestine, have significant expression of the ACE2 receptor. SARS-CoV-2 causes gastrointestinal symptoms by replicating in intestinal epithelial cells after invasion. Changes in intestinal flora can be exacerbated by SARS-CoV-2's bloodstream entrance, which can also lead

to increased platelet and inflammatory cytokine activation. This can disrupt the intestinal flora and cause the gut-blood barrier to break down. As the condition progresses, a variety of symptoms may appear [3].

An enormous population of microorganisms, estimated to number more than 10^{14} cells, colonizes the gastrointestinal (GI) tract [4]. These organisms include bacteria, archaea, viruses, and fungi, but bacteria are the most abundant and best studied. Bacteroidetes and Firmicutes are the two predominant bacterial phyla prevalent in a healthy gut, with Actinobacteria, Proteobacteria, Fusobacteria, and Verrucomicrobia contributing less [4, 5].

Microbial exposure during early life is crucial, as the diversity and stability of the gut microbiota help establish immunoregulatory networks and protect against allergic and inflammatory diseases later in life [11]. Over time, the microbiota and host immune system co-evolve, creating a state of mutual regulation in which microbes both induce immune responses and promote tolerance to harmless antigens [12,16,18]. The gut microbiota influences both innate and adaptive pathways, supporting antigen-presenting cell and neutrophil function while also guiding CD4⁺ T cell responses [13,14,17]. A shift in the gut microbiota's composition can have either a pathological or beneficial effects, mediated by the gut microbiota's regulation of specific CD4 + T cell subtypes [15].

Taken together, these findings highlight that the gut microbiota is not only central to digestion and metabolism but is also a critical regulator of immune homeostasis. The balance between different microbial groups and their metabolites plays a direct role in determining whether the immune system promotes tolerance or shifts toward harmful inflammation.

SARS-CoV-2 affects the gastrointestinal tract by targeting intestinal epithelial cells, leading to dysbiosis and downstream immune alterations. Similarly, inactivated SARS-CoV-2 vaccines have been shown to reshape gut microbial composition and function, with notable differences in abundance and metabolic pathways observed between vaccinated and unvaccinated individuals [37,38,39]. COVID-19 vaccination has been shown to significantly influence gut microbiota composition, leading to reduced bacterial diversity and enrichment of taxa such as *Faecalibacterium* and *Mollicutes* [40]. The gut microbiota may enhance or reduce the efficacy of vaccines through variations in metabolite composition. In addition to affecting gut microbiota abundance and composition, COVID-19 vaccines may reduce the gut microbiota biodiversity [41].

Discussion. It was observed that SARS-CoV-2 infection causes gastrointestinal symptoms as well as may alter gut microflora. [12-30],[33] The study found a relationship between microbiome changes and post-COVID complications, particularly the spread of antimicrobial resistance (AMR).[34-39] Apart from that, it has been discovered that AMR Enterobacteriaceae, specifically *Klebsiella* sp., increased even in moderate instances. [38-45] In mouse models, post-COVID microbiota was related with worsened lung injury and increased susceptibility to *K. pneumoniae*, indicating microbiota-driven pulmonary immune impairment.[46-51] Apart from that, it was revealed that systemic effects went beyond the lungs: post-COVID microbiota increased memory impairment in rats, indicating a gut-brain and lung-brain connection. [52-58] Reduced short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) in donors and mice were proposed as a potential mechanism for neurological and pulmonary effects.[14,59],[60] Additional findings included elevated I-FABP, enrichment of Lachnospiraceae, neuroinflammation (hippocampal TNF), and decreased neuroplasticity markers such as BDNF and PSD-95. [61-65] As a proof of concept, the study found that probiotic *B. longum* 51A reduced memory impairment in a coronavirus mouse model, indicating the therapeutic potential of microbiome-targeted therapies. [23],[29],[66],[67]. These interactions are summarized in Figure 1, which illustrates the proposed post-COVID gut–lung–brain pathway.

Figure 1. Mechanistic Pathway of Post-COVID Microbiota Effects

Despite limitations like as a limited sample size and the lack of virome analysis [8],[68-70] concludes that gut microbiota modifications directly contribute to post-COVID symptoms and AMR spread, emphasising the need of characterising SARS-CoV-2 impacts on the microbiome. [71] It is reported that the first investigation of both bacterial and fungal gut microbiome changes in people recovering with mild COVID-19. The significant, however, microbial changes were observed in Hainan cohorts at 3 months (C3M) and 6 months (C6M) after recovery, which persisted when compared to never-infected controls. Validation in an Inner Mongolia cohort verified the findings' generalisability, suggesting that long-term microbiome alterations occurred regardless of age, gender, or BMI. These changes were associated with gastrointestinal and metabolic problems. Additionally, study reports that advances prior bacterial-centric investigations [72] by incorporating fungal dynamics. [73] found that stage-specific mycobiome alterations, such as a *Kluyveromyces*-to-*Asterotremella* transition, were related with improved AST/ALT ratios ($\beta=-0.42$, 95%CI -0.68 to -0.16; $P=0.008$), expanding findings beyond bacterial frameworks. In comparison to previous single-region models [74], cross-regional validation demonstrated the robustness of a 10-taxa bacterial model (AUC=0.90 Inner Mongolia; AUC=0.99 Hainan). Fungal communities offered comparable predictive benefit (combined AUC=0.61; $P=0.007$), despite their spatial variation (AUC=0.80 vs. 0.65). A dual-domain paradigm for tracking post-viral microbiome recovery was supported by the near-perfect prediction accuracy (AUC=0.99) attained by bacterial and fungal characteristics combined.

The study found that mild COVID-19 causes long-lasting bacterial shifts, which is in line with previous reports [75-85] Upadhyay et al. Alpha diversity did not fully return to baseline, although it did recover somewhat. Gut barrier and metabolic recovery were linked to probiotic taxa that were enriched at C3M, such as *Blautia massiliensis*, *Eubacterium ventriosum*, and *Coprococcus comes* [86-93]. Previously associated with anti-inflammatory and metabolic effects, *Weissella confusa*, *Phocaeicola vulgatus*, and *Streptococcus thermophilus* dominated at C6M. [93-98] Functions in tryptophan metabolism and anti-inflammatory pathways were validated by functional studies. Opportunistic species such *Slackia piriformis* and *Streptococcus equinus*, however, continued to exist, which may have consequences for anaemia and tumours [99, 100, 101]. The fungal component was noticed by a shift from probiotic *Kluyveromyces* in C3M, which might be related with improvement in gut microflora, to anti-inflammatory *Asterotremella* in C6M. Although transient *Kazachstania* indicated possible early immune modulation, opportunistic fungi such as *Alternaria* were highlighted as concerning [104], [105]. *Streptococcus thermophilus* and MCHC [107], [108], and *Asterotremella* and AST/ALT increase [106] were clinically correlated. By using co-occurrence network analysis, Synergistic *Rothia-Coprinopsis* interactions against infections were discovered [109], [110]. The study applied

machine learning approaches to identify recovery signals for bacteria (AUC=0.99) and fungi (AUC=0.80), which were then validated in different geographical areas. These biomarkers have been suggested as potential tools for personalised probiotic or nutritional therapy to address long-term microbiome imbalance. It underlined the importance of longitudinal, intervention-based research while recognising limitations such as the cross-sectional design and the exclusion of long-term COVID cases.

Conclusion. The findings analyzed in the article demonstrate that even patients with mild SARS-CoV-2 infection exhibit significant and long-lasting alterations in the bacterial and fungal composition of the gut microbiota. This dysbiosis is characterized by a reduction in short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), an increased abundance of antimicrobial-resistant microorganisms such as *Klebsiella*, and notable shifts in the mycobiome. Such changes are closely associated with gastrointestinal, metabolic, respiratory, and neurological disturbances, thereby underscoring the clinical and pathogenetic relevance of the “gut–lung–brain axis.” During the recovery phase, the observed enrichment of specific probiotic groups highlights the therapeutic potential of microbiota-targeted interventions in restoring immune stability, alleviating post-COVID gastrointestinal and cognitive complications, and enhancing vaccine efficacy. Furthermore, evidence obtained from studies conducted across different regions, including Uzbekistan, substantiates the reliability and generalizability of these outcomes. This, in turn, expands the prospects of employing microbiota-based biomarkers to monitor post-COVID recovery. At the same time, the necessity of large-scale, longitudinal studies in Uzbekistan and beyond is emphasized, in order to elucidate causal relationships and to evaluate the effectiveness of individualized probiotic and diet-based interventions.

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